

A TASK-TECHNOLOGY FIT VIEW OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: IMPACT ON STUDENT LEARNING

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Introduction

The implementation of Learning Management Systems (LMS) has been one of the most important innovations in the use of information technology in universities around the globe over the past century. A vital component of modern teaching/learning experience is the use of learning management systems. This innovation was quickly adopted in higher education, whether it is distance or face to face and undergraduate or graduate learning (Falvo & Johnson 2007). LMS is a web-based software application that is designed to handle learning content, student interactions, assessments and reports of learning progress and student activities (Kasim & Khalid 2016). Studies have found a positive impact on students' technology use and academic performance (Kim *et al* 2017).

However, much of LMS related research has focused only on technology and mostly limited to technology adoption studies. Task-technology fit is one factor identified to have affected both the use of information systems and the outcomes of information systems (McGill & Klobas 2009). In relation to task technology fit, Technology-to-performance chain (TPC) by Goodhue & Thompson's (1995) is such a model. They suggested that an explanation of the achievements of an information system should acknowledge the technology that is being used and the fit between task and technology (Dale & Ronald, 1995). However, there is a lack of aggregated models to examine the impact of the task- technology fit view of learning management systems on student learning in the Sri Lankan context. Thus, the purpose of this study was to examine the impact of task-technology fit view of learning management system on student learning in Sri Lanka to narrow the identified research gap. The main research question investigated in the current study was “What is the influence of task-technology fit on perceived student learning?”

Methodology

This study attempted to answer the question, “What is the influence of task-technology fit on perceived student learning?” To answer the research question, this study followed a quantitative survey research design. Cross-sectional data collection method was used in this study. Due to time constraint, a convenient sampling method was used in data collection. Data were collected from students in the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce, University of Sri Jayewardenepura. The population was LMS users in the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. Study participants were contacted through the world wide web via google forms and physical questionnaires were distributed among students in the lecture halls. The questionnaire consisted of nineteen questions that could be completed approximately 10 minutes. A seven-point Likert scale anchored from ‘Strongly Agree’ to ‘Strongly disagree’ was used in the questionnaire as the majority of similar studies have used the seven-point Likert scale. In this study already validated questions from McGill and Klobas (2009) were used. 157 usable responses were taken for the analysis after removing incomplete responses. Descriptive data were analyzed using SPSS (Version 25) and the model constructs were analyzed using structural equation modelling with SmartPLS (Version 3.0) software.

Results and Discussion

Two hypotheses were tested to find out the impact of task technology fit of Learning Management System on student learning among undergraduates of the FMSC (see Figure 1). According to the findings, Task Technology Fit has a significant positive influence on perceived student learning ($\beta = 2.758$, $p = 0.006$). LMS Utilization also had a significant positive influence on perceived student learning ($\beta = 6.180$, $p = 0.000$).

Figure 1: Research Model with results

This finding is consistent with previous studies (Staples & Seddon 2004; Goodhue,1997). Goodhue, the framework for the study was used and it supported the usefulness of the model in e-learning. Staples & Seddon found Task-technology fit had a substantial beneficial impact on the anticipated use effects and use attitudes.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the Task-technology fit view of LMS impact on student learning. The sample was undergraduate students of the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce. Both Task Technology Fit and LMS Utilization had a significant positive influence on perceived student learning.

Although this study provided important findings, there were few limitations of this study. The sample of this study was from a single faculty of a university in Sri Lanka. The small number of respondents (157) also was seen as a limiting factor of this study. Thus, the generalization of the study findings is not possible. Therefore, future research is recommended to study a representative larger sample. Also, to generalize these findings more research is needed. Further, future research could extend the model with additional constructs. The current study examined the LMS usage only from the learner's perspective. In the future, a study lecturer's perspective would provide more meaningful findings. However, the findings of this study would be very useful to lecturers and administrators of higher education institutions.

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